

Multiscale and Multiphysics Modelling and Characterisation of Structural Batteries

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Example – Aircraft Interior

Image: Prof Emile Greenhalgh Imperial College London

Example – Aircraft Interior

VS.

Interior panel, 2 x 1.5 m
Glass fiber / phenolic, mass 2.8 kg
Li-ion battery, mass 0.63 kg

Multifunctional interior panel, 2 x 1.5 m
Structural battery, mass 1.13 kg
Weight saving 67 %

The All-Carbon Fibre Based Structural Battery

A laminated structural battery composite

Resin-infused cells

The positive electrode

Bagged cell before infusion

Cured cell

Multifunctional Performance

The Carbon Fiber-Based Electrodes

Capacity and Coulombic Efficiency of Carbon Fiber Negative Electrodes

Effects of lithiation of the Carbon Fiber

Negative half-cell

Image courtesy: Marcus Johansen

Carbon fibre electrode in liquid electrolyte elongation

Effect of lithiation on carbon fibre volume and moduli

An electro-chemo-mechanically coupled material

The negative half-cell

Electro-chemo-mechanically coupled computational modelling of structural batteries

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Negative half-cell

Model representation

Half-cell: Governing equations

Electrolyte (SBE)

(M) $-\sigma \cdot \nabla = 0$ in $\Omega_e \times \mathbb{R}^+$

(E) $-i_{MAX} \cdot \nabla = 0$ in $\Omega_e \times \mathbb{R}^+$

(C) $-\partial_t c_{Li} - j_{Li} \cdot \nabla = 0$ in $\Omega_e \times \mathbb{R}^+$

(C) $-\partial_t c_X - j_X \cdot \nabla = 0$ in $\Omega_e \times \mathbb{R}^+$

Fibres

(M) $-\sigma \cdot \nabla = 0$ in $\Omega_f \times \mathbb{R}^+$

(C) $-\partial_t c_{Li} - j_{Li} \cdot \nabla = 0$ in $\Omega_f \times \mathbb{R}^+$

*(M)echanical, (E)lectrical and (C)hemical response

Half-cell: Implementation

Strong format + constitutive relations + BCs

Weak format (mixed formulation)

Potentiostatic cycling

$$\int_{\Omega_f \cup \Omega_e} \sigma : \epsilon[\delta u] dV = 0 \quad \forall \delta u \in \hat{U}^0$$

$$\int_{\Omega_e} i_{MAX} \cdot \nabla[\delta \varphi] dV + \int_{\Gamma_{fe}} i_{Max,n} \delta \varphi dS - \int_{\Gamma_+} i_{Max,n} \delta \varphi dS = 0 \quad \forall \delta \varphi \in \hat{F}^0$$

$$-\frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_{\Omega_f \cup \Omega_e} [c_{Li} - n^{-1} c_{Li}] \delta \mu_{Li} dV + \int_{\Omega_f \cup \Omega_e} j_{Li} \cdot \nabla[\delta \mu_{Li}] dV$$

$$+ \int_{\Gamma_{fe}} j_{Li,n} [\delta \mu_{Li}] dS - \int_{\Gamma_+} j_{Li,n} \delta \mu_{Li} dS = 0 \quad \forall \delta \mu_{Li} \in \hat{M}_{Li}^0$$

$$-\frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_{\Omega_e} [c_X - n^{-1} c_X] \delta \mu_X dV + \int_{\Omega_e} j_X \cdot \nabla[\delta \mu_X] dV = 0 \quad \forall \delta \mu_X \in \hat{M}_X^0$$

$$\int_{\Omega_f \cup \Omega_e} [\mu_{Li}^{en} - \mu_{Li}] \delta c_{Li} dV = 0 \quad \forall \delta c_{Li} \in L_2(\Omega_f \cup \Omega_e)$$

$$\int_{\Omega_e} [\mu_X^{en} - \mu_X] \delta c_X dV = 0 \quad \forall \delta c_X \in L_2(\Omega_e)$$

Electro-chemo-mechanical analysis

Structural battery design

Electro-chemo-mechanical framework

Electro-chemo-mechanical analysis

Electrochemical analysis

Two-way
coupling

Mechanical analysis

Multiphysics analysis – Internal stresses

Coupling between mechanical stress and chemical potential

Example: fibres (active electrode material)

Effect of Mechanical Load on Voltage

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Method in place to characterise performance under combined loads

Effect of applied load on electric potential for the structural battery full cell

The Structural Positive Electrode

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<https://www.eurekalert.org/multimedia/1041190>

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The LFP-coated Carbon Fiber Electrode

The LFP-coated Fibers

Capacity of the Structural Positive Electrode

Structural Battery Electrolytes

Homogenous systems

- Ion transport depend on polymer chain mobility
- Two competing properties

Inhomogeneous systems

- One phase → Stiffness
- One phase → Conductivity

Structural battery electrolyte

Structural battery electrolyte

Conventional 2D image is lacking information for a porous system.

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FIB

Milling machine

SEM Viewport

Structural battery electrolyte

SBE

Cross section images

3D model

Topology analysis:

Diameter and volume

Polymer

Pore

Topology analysis:

Geodesic tortuosity

$$\text{Geodesic tortuosity} = \frac{\text{Length of the shortest path}}{\text{Length of the Euclidean path}}$$

Dense graph in polymer

	Geodesic tortuosity
x-direction	1.79
y-direction	1.81
z-direction	1.72

FEM Simulation

	Measured	Numerical prediction
Elastic modulus [MPa]	611	738
Ionic conductivity [mS/cm]	0.134	0.633

Summary of research activities on structural battery composites @ Chalmers

Structural Battery Cells

Structural Electrodes

Demonstration

Structural Electrolytes

Material Models

Performance Analysis & LCA

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